

Analysis of survival curves: a compendium of methods for managing restricted mean survival time and mean lifetime survival in the context of a Bayesian network meta-analysis

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In the analysis of published evidence, new methodological approaches are increasingly being used. Among these new methods, the combination of restricted mean survival time (RMST) and bayesian network meta-analysis (NETMA) has already been tested in numerous articles. In some cases, mean lifetime survival (MLS) has been estimated along with RMST.

Three techniques are actually employed in this methodological context because a prerequisite for RMST estimation based on published studies is that individual patient data are reconstructed from the original Kaplan-Meier graph.

In this preprint, we summarize the main methodological aspects of this combined approach (1. Reconstructing patient-level data from Kaplan-Meier survival curves; 2. Estimation of RMST and MLS; 3. 4. Bayesian network meta-analysis; 5. Iconographic presentation of NETMAs) and we provide an extensive bibliography on these topics.

Reconstructing patient-level data from Kaplan-Meier survival curves

The first three phases in the analysis of each Kaplan-Meier curve were the following: i) retrieving the published graphs of the survival curves; ii) estimating the survival percentage-vs-time data points with a digitizer (WebPlotDigitizer. <https://automeris.io/WebPlotDigitizer>); iii) reconstructing patient-level data. For this latter purpose, we used an iterative least squares technique [1] that performs this reconstruction from the total number of events, the total number of at risk patients, and the distribution of at risk patients at over time. Deriving a confidence interval for RMST requires distinguishing censored observations from uncensored observations; hence, when reconstructing individual patient data, reconstruction required not only determining the survival time but also whether the observation was censored or not. The total number of events was retrieved from the text or the figures reported in the original trial; the total number of censored

patients was determined as the difference between the total number of enrolled patients minus the number of events minus the residual number of at risk patients at the closure date of the study. Both these estimates were distributed across the time intervals of the survival curve according to a criterion of iterative minimization of root mean squared error [2] between fitted points and original points of the survival curve.

Estimation of RMST and MLS

After reconstructing each curve, the “survRM2” package [3] was run under the R-platform to determine the value of RMST along with its 95%CI. For this purpose, the so-called milestone was implemented in the R model to indicate the time-point in the follow-up at which the analysis is “restricted” or truncated.

To extend the survival analysis over a lifetime horizon, we also determined the mean lifetime survival (MLS) from the same Kaplan-Meier curves examined to determine RMST. MLS was modeled according to the Weibull distribution [4] as implemented in the “eha” package under the R-platform.

Bayesian network meta-analysis

Bayesian network meta-analysis (NETMA) had the purpose to carry out all direct and indirect comparisons between the treatments. The end-point was represented by the RMST which was handled as a continuous parameter. Binary comparisons were represented as mean difference (MD) of the two RMST values, along with 95% credible interval [CrI]. The approach implemented by this type of NETMA is iterative, and employs Monte Carlo iterations. All of these analyses were conducted using the software package WinBUGS 1.4.3 (Cambridge, UK) in combination with the meta-analysis code developed by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) [4-6].

A Bayesian NETMA can be handled through either the fixed-effect model or the random-effect model. The random-effect model is designed for data sets characterised by some degree of heterogeneity in the clinical material whereas the fixed-effect model should be preferred when heterogeneity is low. To make a decision between these two models, preference can be given to the one that determines the best fit according to the deviance information criterion (DIC) [5,6]. In the package developed by NICE, the ranking in effectiveness across the comparators conforms to surface under the cumulative ranking curve (SUCRA) approach and related graphs.

Iconographic presentation of NETMA

The so-called “simplified figure” [7-9] is the iconographic method employed in our NETMA.

In the field of network meta-analysis, the issue of graphical communication is complex, and the debate is still ongoing [10-16]. While the objective of describing the network geometry is quite straightforward [10,11], communication becomes more complex when it comes to presenting the results of the analysis [12-16]. The graphical proposal described herein is aimed at presenting the network geometry along with the results of the analysis. In our view, despite some degree of unavoidable complexity, this tool deserves to be used particularly when the number of comparators is small.

Conclusions

The RMST is increasingly being recognised as an appropriate methodological standard for analyzing survival curves [17]. This preprint offers a series of references that facilitate the application of this statistical technique

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